

DATA README

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The codes in this replication package solve a quantitative version of the model. The master code runs all other codes that estimate shocks from the data, solve the model under the two calibrations, and generate the figures from the paper. It takes less than 5 minutes on a standard desktop to replicate all results.

1 Data Sources

All data sources were accessed for verification on July 20, 2025.

We use monthly and quarterly data for Russia, the U.S. and the EA from January 2021 to September 2024 that can be freely downloaded from [IFS \(2024\)](#); [FRED \(2024\)](#); [ROSSTAT \(2024\)](#); [CBR \(2024\)](#); [STATISTA \(2024\)](#); [ECB \(2024\)](#).

Exchange Rates, Russia

The paper uses daily exchange rate series of RUB to USD from the [CBR \(2024\)](#). The data can be downloaded freely for available days: “Dynamics of the official exchange rates, Table, Currency: US Dollar” from https://www.cbr.ru/eng/currency_base/dynamics/?UniDbQuery.Posted=True&UniDbQuery.so=1&UniDbQuery.mode=1&UniDbQuery.date_req1=&UniDbQuery.date_req2=&UniDbQuery.VAL_NM_RQ=R01235&UniDbQuery.From=06.03.2020&UniDbQuery.To=08.03.2025. A copy of the data is provided in column “curs” of the file.

Datafile: `Data_daily.csv`

Imports and Exports, Russia

The paper uses data on imports and exports for Russian Federation from the [CBR \(2024\)](#). The name of the database is “Merchandise Trade of the Russian Federation (Balance of Payments Methodology)”. The names of the variables in the database are “Import of goods (FOB), Total” and “Export of goods (FOB)”. The data can be downloaded freely from https://www.cbr.ru/eng/statistics/macro_itm/external_sector/etg/. A copy of the data is provided in the columns “exports” and “imports” of the file.

Datafile: `Data_monthly.csv`

Central Bank of Russia International Reserves

The paper uses data on Central Bank of Russia international reserves from the [CBR \(2024\)](#). The name of the database is “International Reserves of the Russian Federation (End of period)”. The name of the variable in the database is “international reserves”. The data can be downloaded freely from https://www.cbr.ru/eng/hd_base/mrrf/mrrf_m/. A copy of the data is provided in the column “cb_international_reserves”.

Datafile: Data_monthly.csv

Consumer Price Index, Russia

The data comes from the [ROSSTAT \(2024\)](#) (Statistical Agency of Russian Federation) database. The name of the variable in the database is “Consumer Price Index of goods and services”. The data can be downloaded freely from <https://rosstat.gov.ru/statistics/price#> (monthly). A copy of the data is provided in column “cpi_ru” of the file.

Datafile: Data_monthly.csv

Consumer Price Index, United States

The data comes from [FRED \(2024\)](#) database. The name of the variable in the database is “Consumer Price Index For All Urban Consumers: All Items in U.S. City Average, Index 1982-1984=100, Seasonally Adjusted”. The data can be downloaded freely from <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/CPIAUCSL> (monthly). A copy of the data is provided in column “cpi_us” of the file.

Datafile: Data_monthly.csv

Commodity Export Price Index, Russia

The data comes from [IFS \(2024\)](#) IMF database. The name of the variable in the database is “Commodity export price index, individual commodities weighted by ratios of exports to total commodity exports, June 2012 = 100”. The data can be downloaded freely from <https://legacydata.imf.org/?sk=2cddccb8-0b59-43e9-b6a0-59210d5605d2> (monthly). A copy of the data is provided in column “com_exp_index” of the file.

Datafile: Data_monthly.csv

Interest Rate on Euro Deposits, Russia

The paper uses data on interest on individual euro deposits in Russia from the [CBR \(2024\)](#). The name of the database is “Weighted Average Interest Rates on Deposits of Individuals and Nonfinancial Organizations in Euros”. The name of the variable in the database is “Deposits of individuals by maturity, up to 1 year (including demand deposits)”. The data can be downloaded freely from https://www.cbr.ru/eng/statistics/bank_sector/int_rat/. A copy of the data is provided in the column “interest_rus”.

Datafile: Data_monthly.csv

Euribor 1-year Rate

The data comes from the [ECB \(2024\)](#) database. The name of the variable in the database is “Euribor 1-year - Historical close, average of observations through period, Euro area (changing composition), Monthly”. The data can be downloaded freely from https://data.ecb.europa.eu/data/datasets/FM/FM.M.U2.EUR.RT.MM.EURIBOR1YD._HSTA (monthly). A copy of the data is provided in column “interest_eur”.

Datafile: `Data_monthly.csv`

Real GDP, Russia

The data comes from the [ROSSTAT \(2024\)](#) (Statistical Agency of Russian Federation) database. The name of the variable in the database is “Real GDP in 2021 prices for Russia, mlrd (bil) rubles”. The data can be downloaded freely from <https://rosstat.gov.ru/statistics/accounts#> (quarterly). A copy of the data is provided in column “real_gdp_ru” of the file.

Datafile: `Data_quarterly.csv`

Annualised Growth of Real GDP in the United States

The data comes from the [STATISTA \(2024\)](#), but originally is sourced from BEA. The name of the variable in the database is “Annualized growth of real GDP in the United States, SA”. The data can be downloaded freely from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/188185/percent-change-from-preceding-period-in-real-gdp-in-the-us/> (quarterly). A copy of the data is provided in column “real_gdp_an_gr_sa_us” of the file.

Datafile: `Data_quarterly.csv`

Balance of Payments, Russia

The paper uses data from the balance of payments in Russia from the [CBR \(2024\)](#). The name of the database is “Balance of Payments”. The data can be downloaded freely from https://cbr.ru/eng/statistics/macro_itm/external_sector/pb/. The two variables of interest are constructed as follows. In the Financial Account, all rows labeled as “net acquisitions” are aggregated into outflows (changes in foreign assets) and all rows labeled as “net incurrences” are aggregated into inflows (changes in country’s liabilities). A copy of the data is provided in columns “assets_flow” and “liabilities_flow” respectively.

Datafile: `Data_quarterly.csv`

Statement about Rights

- I certify that the author(s) of the manuscript have legitimate access to and permission to use the data used in this manuscript.
- I certify that the author(s) of the manuscript have documented permission to redistribute/publish the data contained within this replication package.

Table 1: List of data files

Data file	Source	Provided	Notes
Data_daily.csv	CB	Yes	
Data_monthly.csv	IMF, CB, ECB, FRED ROSSTAT	Yes	
Data_quarterly.csv	STATISTA, ROSSTAT, CB	Yes	

Note: IMF refers to [IFS \(2024\)](#), STATISTA refers to [STATISTA \(2024\)](#), ROSSTAT refers to [ROSSTAT \(2024\)](#), CB refers to [CBR \(2024\)](#), FRED refers to [FRED \(2024\)](#), ECB refers to [ECB \(2024\)](#).

Summary of Availability

- All data **are** publicly available.
- Some data **cannot be made** publicly available.
- No data can be made** publicly available.

2 Computations

2.1 Computational requirements

- All codes were run on 8GB Apple M1 desktop with MacOS version 15.2
- Matlab R2024b with standard packages
- Approximate time needed to reproduce fully the analysis is less than 5 minutes.
- Figures are generated and saved in .eps format and can be opened with Latex, Adobe Reader, EPS Viewer, etc.

2.2 Description of codes

- `Master.m` is the main file that generates all necessary numbers and figures.
- `Data.m` cleans data, computes required time shocks and other time series for further analysis.
- `Model.m` solves the model under alternative calibrations and decomposes the resulting series into different shocks.
- `Figures.m` computes the empirical moments and makes the figures.
- `IRF.m` produces the impulse responses from the ex-ante model.

2.3 Instructions to replicators

1. Download folders “Data” and “Codes”, create a parallel folder “Figures”.
2. Open and run `Master.m` in Matlab. All figures will be saved in a separate folder “Figures”. The rest of the instructions comment on what each code does.

Table 2: List of tables and figures

Fig/Tab	Code	Output file
Figure 1	<code>Figures.m</code>	USD
Figure 2	no data	
Figure 3	<code>IRF.m</code>	IRF_b, IRF_e
Figure 4	<code>Figures.m</code>	ER_model_data
Figure 5	<code>Figures.m</code>	NER_decomposition_ex-ante, NER_decomposition_ex-post
Figure 6	<code>Figures.m</code>	TR_decomposition, Decomposition_u
Figure 7	<code>Figures.m</code>	Decomposition_u_ Decomposition_cpi_
Table A1	no data	
Figure A1	<code>Figures.m</code>	NER_decomposition_ex-post_MIT, NER_decomposition_kappa_0
Figure A2	<code>Figures.m</code>	Decomposition_cpi
Figure O1	no data	
Figure O2	<code>Figures.m</code>	PPI, Output, Exports, Imports, Financial
Figure O3	<code>Figures.m</code>	Spreads
Figure O4	<code>Figures.m</code>	Liabilities, ER_liabilities

Note: output files show the names of .eps/.pdf files for figures.

- `Data.m` transforms raw data into model's inputs. Quarterly series are adjusted for seasonality and converted into monthly series, nominal variables are adjusted for inflation, trade data and commodity prices are smoothed with HP filter, most series are demeaned by pre-war values, and the exchange rate is adjusted to capture volatile dynamics in the first months. Parameters and time series are saved in `Parameters.mat`, `Shocks.mat` and `Series.mat`.
- `Model.m` solves the model using the Blanchard-Kahn method. The ex-ante calibration relies on AR(1) process for all shocks. The ex-post calibration relies on perfect foresight or unexpected permanent shocks. The resulting decomposition of the exchange rates into different shocks is saved in `Output.mat`. The ex-post calibration also produces financial shocks that rationalize the remaining part of the exchange rate not explained by other shocks. These series are added to `Shocks.mat` and `Series.mat`.
- `Figures.m` uses the estimates from previous steps to produce all figures except for Figures 2, 3 and A5. Figures 2 and A5 are just diagrams, so the codes are not provided.
- `IRF.m` produces impulse responses shown in Figure 3 based on the ex-ante calibration with different values of $\bar{\kappa}$.

References

CBR (2024): “Central Bank Database,” The Central Bank of the Russian Federation, https://www.cbr.ru/eng/hd_base/.

ECB (2024): “ECB Data Portal,” ECB, <https://data.ecb.europa.eu/data>.

FRED (2024): “Federal Reserve Economic Data,” Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, <https://fred.stlouisfed.org>.

IFS (2024): “International Financial Statistics,” International Monetary Fund (IMF), <https://data.imf.org/regular.aspx?key=61545850>.

ROSSTAT (2024): “Russian Statistics,” Federal State Statistics Service, <https://rosstat.gov.ru>.

STATISTA (2024): “STATISTA Database,” STATISTA, <https://www.statista.com>.